

INTERPRETATION PROCESS IN ONLINE MEDIA

Iroda Nasimova¹, Dilrabo Egamberdiyeva²

¹Journalism and mass media in Uzbekistan
University of Communications

²Magistr of Journalism and mass media in Uzbekistan
University of Communications

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the possibilities of the online media world, the benefits of working with information sources, and the interpretation of traditional and modern genres.

The online media space, which offers thousands of convenient ways to get visual information, numbers, and information, is expanding year by year, and it is never going backwards. We live in a time when any source of information, with an audience of millions of subscribers, will one day, at least a second behind the big streams, take the place of new waves.

Today, the Internet has formed the core that carries out interactions between different data networks around the world. Where once it served only research and teaching teams, today it is widespread among the production circles. Companies are attracted by the speed of the Internet, low cost, comprehensive communication, ease of collaboration, software that allows everyone to work, and a unique database.

For a low service fee, users have access to commercial or non-commercial information services in the United States, Canada, Australia, and many other European countries.

From the freely accessible archives of the Internet, you can find information that covers all aspects of human activity, from the latest scientific news to the weather forecast for tomorrow. Especially for individuals, organizations, institutions that need daily communication, the use of Internet infrastructure is much cheaper than direct communication over the phone. This is especially convenient for firms that have branches abroad, as the confidential unique connections of the Internet are available all over the world.

It consists of the constant collection, processing and dissemination of popular information around the world through the Internet, which is the main information channel, and it is one of the means of mass propaganda and advocacy. The information disseminated by him must have its own "audience" in the language of the university, be able to socially orient his public and worldviews, the laws of modern reality, diversity, the basic laws governing the socio-economic development of society.

Information journalism is a tool between its audience, which should serve to address the diverse problems it poses as a political institution of journalism. The term "media" is based on this.

The differences between online journalism and traditional journalism are as follows:

- Interactivity - this feature is embodied in the Internet technology itself, which provides its multi-faceted "network" connection.

- Professional approach - it allows each student or group to take into account their personal views, opinions and requirements.

- Instantaneous capability - the advantage of this is that the data transfer rate is extremely high, and the desired information reaches the destination quickly and at the same time with high quality.

- Dimensionality - allows students to quickly and easily determine the level of importance of this or that information.

- Consensus - this means the ability to quickly and easily update the information page, taking into account the views of each visitor.

- Cost-effectiveness - Despite the cost of software in the dissemination of Internet information, the information that each

student needs is delivered faster and cheaper than paper information, and most importantly, quality.

Some researchers say that the internet cannot be considered a full-fledged media, and point to a number of factors as the reasons for this. According to the analysis, the Internet is not a single centralized media, but an environment that includes a variety of structures, including media functions. There are also sites on the Internet whose purpose is only to disseminate information, more precisely, information of social significance.

These include commercial sites offering a variety of products and services, search engines that help search for information on the network, electronic libraries, and more.

The Internet-media was not limited to the transmission of information, but also allowed to establish communication, that is, to know the opinion of the recipient immediately and to make changes to the content of the material accordingly. Internet journalism, along with the press, radio, and television, determines the information policy of a society. Its development is carried out in interaction with other types of media. With the advent of the Internet, the conditions for the preparation and transmission of media have changed. First, media training has lost its uniqueness only to a team of professional journalists. Second, the media is divided into two parts that are inextricably linked. One is the part that transmits information, the other is the part that can receive it and respond immediately.

The use of innovative technologies will help to solve the problems that arise on the Internet and meet the growing demand for information, and at the same time the

individualization of information will rise to a higher level. At the same time, ensuring the right of citizens to information is one of the components of the process of establishing cooperation between government agencies and the population. Today, all media outlets and government agencies have their own "page" on the Internet. This will lead to the acceleration of democratic processes, increase the political activity of the population, increase the effectiveness of relations between the state and society.

Due to its artistic nature, journalism has been included in the literature in a broad sense since ancient times. The literature is traditionally divided into two:

- a) fiction;
- b) journalism.

By itself, the essay genre is a genre related to journalism. But do all the works created in this direction, which combine the features of analysis, research, figurative generalization, belong to journalism? The monograph "Artistic journalistic skills" says: "Any journalistic work is, of course, a journalistic work. But any journalistic work cannot be a journalistic work, it cannot rise to its level. Journalism is more quantitative, and journalism is measured and evaluated by quality. . It covers life more broadly, on a larger scale, develops the idea and grows it to great social conclusions, in this sense, the type of journalistic creativity can be equated with politics, journalism with ideology. It is also possible to use the concepts of "speed", differentiability, relevance, relevance, integrity in relation to journalism.

Although the essay, which is an integral genre of fiction, has not appeared in Uzbek journalism for a long time, it is known that for its development there is a great source for the study of scientific, journalistic, artistic, historical, philosophical, memoir works. Elements of essays (reflection, philosophical thinking, experience) can be found in novels, short stories, short stories, and even pamphlets with a scientific approach.

For example, a person who reads only Ozod Sharafiddinov's scientific articles on literary processes is involuntarily attracted to it as if he were reading a work of art. Researcher Marhabo Kochkarova says in her dissertation: "The most captivating aspect of reading Ozod Sharafiddinov's articles is the very sincere and emotional impact of his style." This characteristic of works of fiction can be found in many articles by Ozod Sharafiddinov. "Literature is the greatest and most glorious of all the miracles, of all the great inventions, that man has discovered. It is a wonderful spring. It is such a spring that it has the purity of tears, the ringing of a girl's bell like a bell, and the color of a rainbow."¹

In short, the most important thing is that the media has become mass communication. Third, the information took on a hypertext structure, meaning that while reading one text, it was possible to move on to other texts that were close to its subject. Anyone looking for material on a particular topic can find many other materials on the Internet.

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